

IMPORTANT PRINCIPLES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article discusses the important principles of physical education and the theory and methodology of physical education.

Key words: principle, didactic, general, objective, fundamental, non-instructive, activity, continuity, individuality, balance, skill, competence.

Among the principles that reflect the ideological foundations of the education and training system, it is possible to include the general social principles of the society regarding the strategy of education. They imply the use of social factors (culture, upbringing, education) to ensure the purposeful all-round development of a person and the integral connection of education with the practical life of society.

The term "principle" refers to the general theoretical conditions that objectively reflect the fundamental laws of education, upbringing and personality, that is, a theoretical doctrine includes worldviews and ideas. The principles of physical education are the social requirements imposed on the educational process, the rules to be followed in the organization and management of education and are followed.

Principle - "Principle" from Latin means foundation

The thread is split in two

1-General principle

2- Didactic principle

The general principle is divided into 3

1 Healing principle

2 The principle of comprehensive development of a person

3 Connection with military operations

The didactic principle deals with learning and teaching aimed at intellectualizing the society and includes learning processes.

Didactic principle includes consciousness, non-instructiveness, activity, individuality principle, continuity principle, balance and adjustment principle, etc.

The principle of non-indicativeness is implemented in the forms of seeing, hearing and moving

The main methodological principles used in the formation of skills and abilities are the same and necessary for everyone, regardless of the age of the students. It is appropriate to point out that physical education is more legitimate to call the principles methodical rather than didactic, since it includes the training of physical qualities and equipping the participants with knowledge. It is necessary for everyone, regardless of the age of the students

In the system of physical education, these principles are the main guiding rules, in accordance with which the entire practice of physical education is carried out.

The principles of physical education guarantee the unity of all aspects of education (mental, moral, aesthetic, labor, physical) in the process of physical education. The greatest health effect: promotes health and ensures good maintenance of general working ability; reflects the main task of physical education in preparing a person for work and other types of activities, including all-round military service.

The most important rules mentioned above are reflected in the general principles of physical education (the principle of all-round development of the individual, the principle of unity of physical education with work and military activity, the principle of orientation to health) There are general pedagogical principles in the education and training system and they reflect the basic laws of teaching (didactics).

They change in the form of general methodological principles in physical education and include a number of universal rules of methodology. Without them, it is impossible to solve the tasks of education and upbringing at a high quality level. In addition to such principles, there are also special principles in the practice of physical education, which are the principles of "rules that determine a number of special laws of physical education and derive from them - its systematic structure". Thus, the main rules in the system of physical education general social and general pedagogical as well as general methodical and special principles are used as well.

The wide-ranging system of physical education includes the family-preschool period (from infancy to kindergarten age), school age, secondary special and higher education period, and physical education of adults (male and female). In Uzbekistan, physical education in secondary schools is considered a pedagogical process and is carried out through physical education classes and

training in sports sections. 2 hours a week physical education classes have been introduced in grades 1-9 according to the "State Education Standard of Physical Education for General Secondary Schools". Special tests were developed in 1999 in order to popularize physical education among students and improve their health.

3-level badges "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" were established for those who successfully passed these tests. 1,588,298 students successfully passed these tests (2002). Also, public competitions "Umid Nihollar" for schoolchildren, "Barkamol Avlod" for lyceum-college students, and "Universiada" for university students were held every 2 years. "Alpomish Games" festival and "Tomaris Games" are held every 2nd year in terms of folk games and public sports.

Only people whose spiritual and physical strength have matured in all respects will be loyal to their Motherland and make a great contribution to its development. All-around perfect people do not appear by themselves. They can become such perfect people under the influence of certain social life conditions, among which education, including physical education, plays a special role. Growing into a well-rounded person is influenced by both biological laws and the need for the harmonious development of the systems and organs of the human body, so that a person is always and everywhere a single social being both socially and in terms of his biological characteristics. is a person. All of this determines the nature of impact on a person from all sides in the process of physical education and determines the organic connection between different types of education.

List of used literature:

1. Abdurasulov J. (2024). HARBIY PEDAGOGIKANING BOSHQA FANLAR BILAN ALOQASI. Молодые ученые, 2(6), 48–52. извлечено от <https://inacademy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/28164>
2. Abdurasulov J., & Pardabayeva , M. (2024). MUSOBAQADAN OLDIN SPORTCHILARNI PSIXOLOGIK TAYYORLASH. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 4(6 Part 2), 73–76. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/34717>
3. Xusanova, N. . (2024). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH DIFFERENT TEMPERAMENTS. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 4(10), 17–20. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/37667>
4. Amangeldiyev, S. . (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY IN OLD AGE: A KEY FACTOR FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING. Евразийский журнал

социальных наук, философии и культуры, 4(10), 12–16. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/37666>

5. Abduqodirova, & Pardaboyeva, M. (2024). THE ROLE OF EMOTIONAL CREATIVITY IN STUDENTS' DECISION-MAKING. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND SOCIAL-HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES, 1(7), 27–30.

<https://universalconference.us/universalconference/index.php/ICNSHS/article/view/2371>

6. Zilola Dilmurodova. (2024). PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL NATURE OF ABILITY. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 27, 1–4. Retrieved from <https://ejird.journalspark.org/index.php/ejird/article/view/1092>

7. Абдусаматова Шахло Саитмуратовна. (2024). РОЛЬ ПСИХОЛОГИИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ У СТУДЕНТОВ. IMRAS, 7(7), 39–43. Retrieved from <https://journal.imras.org/index.php/sps/article/view/1664>

8. Ozodqulov, O. . (2024). VATANPARVARLIK RUHINI TALABALARDA RIVOJLANTIRISH PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. Центральноеазиатский журнал академических исследований, 2(10 Part 2), 37–41. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/cajar/article/view/38469>

9. Zukhra Mirzotilloevna Radjabova. (2023). Features Of Adolescent And Teacher Cooperation In The Current Period In Choosing A Profession. Diversity Research: Journal of Analysis and Trends, 1(3), 210–215. Retrieved from <https://academiaone.org/index.php/2/article/view/131>

